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Main Authors: Marisa Koopmann, Kristian Berwanger, Lina Mebus

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Author(s)	Marisa Koopmann (FIT), Kristian Berwanger (FIT), Lina Mebus (FIT)
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Abstract	<p>This deliverable presents the outcomes of Task T1.1, Multi-Actor and Knowledge Centres Co-Design and Requirements Definition, within Work Package 1 (WP1) of the All Data for Green Deal (AD4GD) project. It builds upon the foundations laid in Deliverable 1.1 and documents the iterative process of refining user requirements for the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS).</p> <p>A central element of this process was the Co-Design Workshop, held in September 2023, which brought together project partners and stakeholders to collaboratively define user needs for two pilot applications—Lake Splashboard and BioConnect—as well as the broader General User Interface of the GDDS. Through participatory design methods, user journeys were created, initial prototypes were developed and user stories extracted. These prototypes were subsequently evaluated by potential end users, leading to the identification of additional user needs and refinement of existing user stories.</p> <p>As a result of this iterative process, a total of 115 user requirements were formulated, 30 requirements for Pilot 1, 49 requirements for Pilot 2 and 34 requirements for the General User Interface of the GDDS.</p> <p>This deliverable concludes the requirements definition phase, providing a</p>
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	structured foundation for the implementation of the GDDS tools. The methodology applied, based on Human-Centered Design (HCD) principles, ensures that user needs remain central throughout the development process.
Keywords	User requirements, user stories, Human-Centred Design, Data Space, Stakeholder Engagement
Disclaimer	Views and opinions expressed in this deliverable are those of the author(s) only, and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the United Kingdom or Switzerland. Neither the European Union nor United Kingdom nor Switzerland can be held responsible for them.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
AU	Aston University
CREAF	Centro De Investigacion Ecologica Y Aplicaciones Forestales
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DGENV	Directorate-General Environment
DGDEFIS	Directorate-General Defence Industry and Space
EC	European Commission
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EEA	European Environment Agency
ESA	European Space Agency
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FIT	Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Information Technology
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GD	Green Deal
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
HCD	Human-Centred Design
IoT	Internet of Things
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KWB	Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin
MEDEEC	Mediterranean Experts on Climate and environmental Change
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium Europe
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WCMC	World Conservation Monitoring Centre
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the outcomes of Task T1.1, Multi-Actor and Knowledge Centres Co-Design and Requirements Definition, within Work Package 1 (WP1) of the All Data for Green Deal (AD4GD) project. It builds on the foundational work of Deliverable 1.1, which laid the groundwork for stakeholder engagement and the initial collection of user needs. Over the past two years, extensive participatory research, co-design activities, and iterative evaluations have been conducted to refine and validate the user requirements for the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS).

The document details the results of an in-person Co-Design Workshop, held in September 2023, where project partners collaboratively explored user needs, developed user journeys, and created initial prototypes. The workshop focused on two pilot applications—Lake Splashboard and BioConnect—as well as the broader General User Interface of the GDDS. User stories were derived from stakeholder discussions and participatory design methods, forming the basis for iterative prototype development.

Following the workshop, an evaluation phase was conducted to assess the usability and functionality of the developed prototypes. Potential end users from relevant domains participated in structured evaluations, providing valuable feedback on the clarity, accessibility, and effectiveness of the proposed solutions. This phase led to a systematic expansion and revision of the identified user stories, ensuring they accurately reflected user expectations and practical use cases. Some initial user stories were revised or removed to maintain alignment with real-world needs.

The final user requirements documented in this deliverable provide a structured foundation for the implementation of the GDDS tools. A total of 115 user requirements were identified:

- 30 for Pilot 1 (Lake Splashboard)
- 49 for Pilot 2 (BioConnect)
- 34 for the General User Interface

The findings presented in this deliverable mark the conclusion of the requirement-gathering phase. The gathered requirements are used as a basis for the implementation in the respective pilot applications and the GDDS platform and will also serve for the evaluation of the tools. The methodological approach outlined in this deliverable —grounded in *Human-Centered Design (HCD)* principles—provides a robust framework for future enhancements and ensures that usability remains at the core of the AD4GD project's objectives.

By systematically engaging stakeholders throughout the design and evaluation process, this deliverable establishes a strong foundation for the successful development of the GDDS tools, contributing to a more accessible, interoperable, and user-friendly *Green Deal Data Space*.

1. INTRODUCTION - PURPOSE & SCOPE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the activities and outcomes related to Task T1.1 - "Multi-actor and knowledge centres co-design and requirements definition" within Work Package 1 (WP1) of the "All Data for Green Deal" project. It builds upon the foundation established in Deliverable 1.1 [1], submitted in February 2023, and incorporates all subsequent activities conducted over the past two years.

Section 1 provides an introduction outlining the structure of this deliverable and presents a concise summary of the key points from Deliverable 1.1, which forms the basis for the current document. This section aims to establish the context and continuity between Deliverable 1.1 and the present work, ensuring a clear understanding of the evolution of Task T1.1 over time.

Section 2 summarizes the primary activities conducted during the Pilot Kick-off Co-Design Workshop, which took place on-site in September 2023 at Fraunhofer FIT with relevant pilot partners. The workshop served as a collaborative forum to establish a shared understanding of pilot objectives, challenges, and initial design directions. During the workshop, an initial set of user stories was derived specifically for Pilot 1, Pilot 2 and the General User Interface.

Section 3 details the outcomes of the evaluation of the prototypes for Pilot 1, Pilot 2, and the General User Interface. Potential end users participated actively in these evaluations, providing critical feedback on the usability, functionality, and relevance of the proposed prototypes. This section particularly highlights additional user stories identified through the evaluation process, reflecting newly discovered user needs. Additionally, it documents user stories that were excluded from consideration based on direct feedback from potential end users, ensuring that the final requirements are closely aligned with actual user needs and expectations.

Section 4 presents a comprehensive list of user requirements identified for Pilot 1, Pilot 2, and the General User Interface. These requirements are based on insights gained from the co-design workshop, prototype evaluations, and stakeholder discussions. The requirements reflect the diverse and specific needs expressed by end-users and stakeholders throughout the iterative co-design process.

Section 5 concludes the deliverable by summarizing the key insights derived from the co-design and evaluation process. It provides a synthesis of the findings, emphasizing the importance of a user-centered approach in shaping the pilots. Additionally, this section outlines clear next steps to be taken in subsequent project phases, ensuring continuity and a structured progression towards the final implementation of the identified user requirements.

1.1 KEY POINTS DELIVERABLE 1.1

Deliverable 1.1, titled "Multi-actor and Knowledge Centres Co-Design and Requirements Definition Report," laid the foundational framework for Task T1.1. It focused on identifying relevant stakeholders, understanding their needs, and establishing an initial set of requirements for the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS).

Key components of Deliverable 1.1 included:

- **Stakeholder Analysis:** An initial workshop was conducted with consortium members to identify and prioritize relevant stakeholders, including global/EU-level actors such as EC Knowledge Centres and local stakeholders relevant to the project pilots. This resulted in a stakeholder map differentiating between data providers and data consumers.
- **Participatory Methods:** The deliverable outlined the use of Human-Centred Design (HCD) principles, combining stakeholder analysis, contextual interviews, and qualitative content

analysis to gather user needs. Workshops and interviews with pilot partners (e.g., KWB and CREAM) were pivotal in understanding specific requirements.

- **Context-of-Use Descriptions:** Based on interviews, two primary user contexts were described: "A Researcher as Data Consumer" and "A Data Provider." These descriptions highlighted workflows, challenges in data management, and the importance of metadata and interoperability.
- **Initial Set of User Stories:** Derived from contextual insights, a first set of 14 user stories were identified differentiating between data consumer and data provider.

Number	User Story	Label
1	As a researcher, I would like to find data by providing a location, because I lack the experience of where to find it (e.g. when I work in an unfamiliar region).	Data Consumer
2	As a researcher, I would like to find data by providing a topic/keyword, because I lack the experience of where to find it (e.g. when I work on a new topic).	Data Consumer
3	As a researcher, I need sufficient metadata because I need to know what the data is about.	Data Consumer
4	As a researcher, I need sufficient metadata because I need to know if the data meets my quality requirements.	Data Consumer
5	As a researcher, I would like to see when the data set was last modified to determine if I have the most recent data.	Data Consumer
6	As a researcher I would like to validate the data, towards various variables (e.g. completeness of dataset), to make sure that the dataset meets my quality requirements.	Data Consumer
7	As a researcher, I need sufficient metadata to know how the data was collected, because I need to understand if the data meets my trustworthiness requirements.	Data Consumer
8	As a researcher, I would like to see who authored the data set to determine if I trust this data provider.	Data Consumer
9	As a researcher, I would like to get all the necessary data from a single point of interaction, so I do not have to ask many different sources.	Data Consumer
10	As a researcher, I need access to historical (meteorological, geological, ..) data to create my models and show changes over time.	Data Consumer
11	As a researcher, I need easy access to private/confidential data without requesting them via email every time.	Data Consumer
12	As a researcher, I would like to get help in combining/harmonising data from different sources because the data sources often do not use standardised formats (e.g. timestamp format, decimal separator, satellite image resolution, ..).	Data Consumer
13	As a researcher, I would like to be able to share my data (preliminary results) with clients and/or project members to get feedback on my work.	Data Provider
14	As a researcher, I would like to share my data/results to contribute to my research community/field.	Data Provider

Table 1. User Stories included in Deliverable 1.1

This deliverable expands on these foundations, documenting the evolution of stakeholder engagement, the refinement of methodologies, and the comprehensive set of requirements identified through continuous collaboration.

While pursuing Task 1.1 and related activities across other work packages, it became evident that the requirements of the pilot partners, as well as the overarching needs of the GDDS, could not be effectively met by a single tool or user interface. This realization was driven by the understanding that the project pilots were designed to tackle specific challenges within the GDDS framework, aiming to enhance the utilization of data and services from a variety of sources. In contrast, the General User Interface would provide access to datasets for participants in the GDDS, allowing for individual analysis, but it would not directly deploy tools for conducting those analyses.

Efforts towards tool and user interface definition are only taken for Pilot 1 and Pilot 2 as well as a General User Interface for the GDDS. Pilot 3 does not involve work on tool development because its primary focus is on evaluating the scientific value of IoT-based observations for air quality monitoring rather than creating a dedicated graphical user interface. Instead of developing a user interface, the emphasis is on establishing a robust data pipeline for integrating and analyzing IoT data. For any visualization needs the pilot partner ECMWF has readily available tools that can be utilized to incorporate new data sets from the AD4GD project.

2. CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP

Based on work reported in Deliverable 1.1 and associated communication with project partners and stakeholders, it became clear that addressing the diverse requirements of pilot partners and the overarching objectives of the GDDS necessitated a targeted and collaborative approach. As the project progressed, stakeholders identified specific challenges related to water quality, biodiversity, and air quality that needed to be tackled through tailored solutions. Recognizing the complexity of these issues, it was essential to engage users and stakeholders directly in the design process to ensure their needs and perspectives were integrated into the development of the tools.

Therefore, a Pilot Kick-off Co-Design workshop took place in person from September 11th to 14th, 2023, at Fraunhofer FIT in Bonn, Germany. This four-day workshop served as a critical milestone in aligning all project partners and stakeholders with a shared understanding of the objectives, challenges and goals of each of the pilots. The primary goal was to establish a comprehensive foundation for further development. To achieve this, dedicated sessions were held where pilot stories for each of the pilots were presented. These presentations included a clear articulation of the problem statement, detailing the specific challenges that the respective pilot aimed to address. Additionally, a solution statement was provided to outline the envisioned approach to tackling these challenges. This structured approach ensured that all participants gained a clear and consistent perspective on the scope and intentions of each pilot.

A fundamental part of the workshop was the creation of user journeys. These visual representations helped to illustrate the pathways a user follows while interacting with a product or service. By mapping out these journeys, the team was able to better understand the user's needs, expectations, and potential pain points. These insights were crucial for refining the pilot concepts and aligning them with user stories. A more detailed examination of the problem and solution statements, as well as the user journeys, is documented in Deliverable 6.1 – Pilot Technical Implementation Planning, Implementation, and Assessment [2].

Building upon the user journey insights, paper prototypes were developed using the design studio method. This method facilitated collaborative brainstorming and iterative design by allowing participants to sketch and refine interface concepts rapidly. The development of these prototypes played a pivotal role in translating conceptual ideas into tangible designs that could be assessed and refined in subsequent project phases. A comprehensive description of the design studio method and the outcomes of the prototyping sessions can be found in Deliverable 5.1 – AI, ML in HPC and Cloud for Fair Science Services [3].

During the creation of these paper prototypes for Pilot 1, Pilot 2, and the General User Interface, a preliminary set of user stories was identified. This process involved thoroughly documenting each screen of the paper prototypes through textual descriptions. These descriptions captured the intended functionalities and interactions, which were then systematically analyzed to derive initial user stories. These user stories encapsulate specific user needs and tasks that the interface should support.

The identified user stories were categorized separately for Pilot 1, Pilot 2, and the General User Interface to ensure clarity and ease of reference. These stories serve as a foundational input for further development and refinement, providing a structured framework for subsequent design and implementation phases. The complete list of derived user stories is provided in the next sections of this document.

2.1 IDENTIFIED USER STORIES – PILOT 1

Number	User Story
1	As a user, I want to get information on the water quality and availability of small lakes in my

	district in Berlin, to decide on actions to maintain or increase its condition.
2	As a user, I want to see the lakes on a map of Berlin, to select lakes that I want to know more about.
3	As a user, I want to search for the name of a lake, to select lakes that I want to know more about.
4	As a user, I want to understand the quality and availability of water, for example by different colouring of the lakes based on their current water quality.
5	As a user, I would like to be able to directly view the water quality of the lakes on the map, for example by specific colouring, so that I can directly view lakes with poor water quality.
6	As a user, I want to see a ranking of the small lakes in Berlin (or in my district) such as the shape of the lake, general information about the lake and the index, to decide whether an action must be implemented for this lake.
7	As a user, I want to compare the current data of this lake to historical data, to understand how the data of the lake changes.
8	As a user, I would like to compare up to 5 small lakes in terms of all values that were also visible in the detail view to identify differences.
9	As a user, I want to see a list of all the small lakes so I can select and deselect the lakes I want to compare.
10	As a user, I would like to be able to search for specific lakes when the list is very long, and I can't look over all the lakes on the interface to select a specific lake.
11	As a user, I want to login to access sensible data on a specific lake and to generate a dashboard based on that data.
12	As a user, I want to add data on different categories like "Fish mortality" and generate a graph on that data, to compare it to other data, for example in the category "rainfall events".

Table 2. Identified User Stories during Pilot Kick-Off Workshop for Pilot 1

2.2 IDENTIFIED USER STORIES – PILOT 2

Number	User Story
1	As a user, I would like to understand what the "BioConnect-Explorer" is about, to decide if it is useful for my working tasks.
2	As a user, I want to actively enter the "BioConnect-Explorer", to avoid opening complex tools that are not useful for me.
3	As a user, I want to upload a geometry file with geolocation data, to find out what effect certain constructions in specific areas would have on animal connectivity.
4	As a user, I want to be guided by instruction when uploading my file, to avoid uploading the wrong format.
5	As a user, I want to select one, or multiple species and show their connectivity in the map, to understand how good the connectivity in my scenario is.
6	As a user, I would like to see the types of data available, such as satellite data, to decide for myself which data to include?
7	As a user, I want to be able to create, rename, delete and share an individual map, to be able to manage multiple scenarios.
8	As a user, I would like to be able to draw a land use scenario to see its impact on connectivity in the set geographic area.

9	As a user, I would like to be able to mark certain areas on the map and, if necessary, leave text comments so that thoughts about the map are documented and not forgotten.
10	As a user, I would like to be able to change the parameter of the created scenario to be able to view different land uses.
11	As a user, I would like to be able to view the connectivity in the scenario over time to also see the future impact.
12	As a user, I would like to see the maps layer in separate maps, side by side, to be able to compare them.
13	As a user, I want to be able to export an image of the current map view, to save the map on my local file system and be able to open it again later.
14	As a user, I want to be able to save images in different formats, for example PDF, Image, Link to current view in the “BioConnect-Explorer”, to be able to open the map later again.

Table 3. Identified User Stories during Pilot Kick-Off Workshop for Pilot 2

2.3 IDENTIFIED USER STORIES – GENERAL USER INTERFACE

To ensure continuity and clear differentiation between the various user stories, we maintain the numbering sequence established in the Deliverable 1.1 for the General User Interface. This approach allows us to track the evolution of user needs more effectively and ensures that newly identified requirements are systematically integrated into the iterative design process.

Number	User Story
15	As a user, I want to be able to directly access the main functionalities “Explore Data”, “Become a Network Member”, “Activities”, “Tools” and login in order to fulfil my task.
16	As a user, I want to understand the functionality of the GDDS, to decide if the GDDS is what I was looking for.
17	As a user, I want to be able to enter a search term to find only the datasets that are relevant in the context of that search term.
18	As a user, I want to save and delete multiple search terms (for example Tags), to find only datasets that are relevant for these search terms.
19	As a user, I want to see different datasets and their location within a map, to select a dataset based on its geographic reference.
20	As a user, I want to select a specific dataset in the map, to open the details on this dataset.
21	As a user, I would like to be able to enter the geographical coordinates to find a specific data set.
22	As a user, I want to filter the datasets based on licences, format, time period and EVs to find datasets that are relevant to me.
23	As a user, I would like to be able to see which datasets were found based on my filter settings in order to view details in the next step.
24	As a user, I would like to know the title, the author, country of publication and EVs of the dataset, to decide if the dataset is relevant to me.
25	As a user, I would like to know if the dataset is protected by any licences and if it is validated, to decide if the dataset is relevant to me.
26	As a user, I would like to receive information about metadata and the data model for the selected dataset in order to determine the quality of the dataset.
27	As a user, I would like to be able to choose to receive the link to the data in order to download the data at the destination.

28	As a user, I want to be able to select a data preview, for example in a map, to better understand the data before downloading.
29	As a user, I would like to be able to select several data sets in a data preview so that I can compare them.
30	As a user, I would like to see an overview and details of the active participants in the Data Space in order to be able to assess how trustworthy these participants are.
31	As a user, I would like to have the opportunity to become a member of the GDDS with my organization in order to participate in the GDDS.
32	As a user, I would like to be able to see how the GDDS has already been used in certain research fields in order to gain inspiration for my research field.
33	As a user, I would like to know publications that are written in context of the GDDS, in order to gain inspiration for my own research.
34	As a user, I would like to understand which tools can be used within the GDDS and what they are about, to decide if they are relevant for my work.
35	As a user, I want to open a link to the tool, for example in GitHub, to access it.
36	As a user, I want to understand more about the licence under which the tool is to be used, to protect myself legally.
37	As a user, I want to enter organization details, an email address and password, in order to login.

Table 4. Identified User Stories during Pilot Kick-Off Workshop for the General User Interface

3. EVALUATION OF PROTOTYPES (PILOT1, PILOT2, GENERAL USER INTERFACE)

To ensure that the solutions developed for the GDDS align with user needs and expectations, we adhere to the Human-Centered Design (HCD) approach as defined in ISO 9241-210 (International Organization for Standardization, 2019) [4]. This methodology has already been outlined in previously submitted deliverables (D1.1, D5.1, and D6.1). In this deliverable, we focus specifically on the continuous refinement of user requirements, which, in our case, are represented as user stories. This ongoing refinement is a fundamental aspect of the iterative HCD process, ensuring that the design evolves in response to user feedback and newly emerging needs.

3.1 PROCEDURE OF EVALUATIONS

During the Pilot Kick-Off Workshop, initial paper prototypes were developed as a first conceptualization of the user interface. These prototypes were then translated into low-fidelity digital prototypes using Figma (Figure 1, Figure 2 & Figure 3), a collaborative web application for interface design, allowing for a more interactive evaluation. The full prototypes can be accessed via the links in the reference section [5, 6, & 7].

Figure 1 Excerpt Low-Fidelity Prototype (Version 2) Splashboard – Tool.

Figure 2 Excerpt Low-Fidelity Prototype (Version 2) BioConnect – Tool.

Figure 3 Excerpt Low-Fidelity Prototype (Version 2) General User Interface – Tool.

The purpose of these low-fidelity prototypes was to facilitate early user testing and feedback collection from potential end users, enabling us to uncover usability issues and identify additional user needs that could be transformed into new user stories.

Given that the prototypes were still at a low-fidelity stage with limited interactive functionality, it was not possible to conduct a standard usability test where users independently complete predefined tasks. Instead, we adopted a walkthrough-based evaluation approach that focused on guided exploration of the prototype by the moderator (Figure 4).

The evaluation began by presenting the prototype to the participants and asking about their initial impressions —what they noticed first and how they interpreted the interface at a glance. As the prototype had only limited functionalities, users were not given free rein to explore but were instead guided through specific screens and interactions. Throughout the evaluation, they were asked expectation-based questions such as: "What do you think will happen if you click on this button?" or "What kind of information do you expect to see on the next screen?" This approach allowed us to assess whether users' mental models aligned with the intended functionality of the interface. Special attention was paid to user behaviours, navigational patterns, and any points of confusion or hesitation. The primary goal of the evaluation was to gather qualitative insights rather than quantitative performance metrics, such as task completion rates. These qualitative insights were essential in refining the interface design and updating user stories to better reflect real-world user expectations.

To ensure that feedback was gathered from relevant stakeholders, participants were selected based on their potential role as end users of the tools. For the evaluation of the Splashboard (Pilot 1 tool), three district office employees in Berlin, responsible for decision-making regarding small urban lakes, were invited. The BioConnect tool (Pilot 2 tool) evaluation included four participants, consisting of technicians of natural park and environmental consultants. Additionally, a project partner (CREAF), who could also potentially be an end user of the GDDS, participated in the evaluation of the general user interface.

Each evaluation session was conducted remotely via screen sharing and lasted between one and two hours. Apart from one session —where two natural park technicians participated together for the BioConnect tool evaluation, —, all other evaluations were conducted individually to minimize bias and ensure that each participant could provide independent feedback.

After the evaluation sessions, the collected feedback was systematically analyzed by both the moderator of the session and a note taker. Key insights were used to refine existing user stories and identify new ones. The analysis focused on recurring themes, usability issues, and user expectations. Key insights included, for example, difficulties in navigating between different sections of the interface, confusion about terminology used, and some ideas about further functionalities. These findings were used to refine existing user stories and identify new ones. In cases where users expected a function to behave differently, new user stories were created to better align the design with their mental models. Additionally, some participants indicated that certain functionalities were unnecessary or irrelevant for their specific use cases, leading to their removal in future design iterations.

Figure 4. Screen shot of evaluation of BioConnect Tool.

The following section presents the newly identified user stories based on user feedback, along with those that were removed or revised in the iteration design iterations. By continuously integrating user insights into the development process, we ensure that the GDDS tools remain intuitive, effective, and aligned with the needs of their intended users. As mentioned before, we maintain the numbering sequence for each of the tools to ensure continuity and clear differentiation between the various user stories.

3.2 IDENTIFIED USER STORIES – PILOT 1

Number	User Story
13	As a user, I want to zoom into the map, if I know a lake's location, to find the lake that I am looking for.
14	As a user, I would like to understand how the Lake Index is built (Measurement period, Parameters, Calculation method, all seasons...), in order to understand how valid the Lake Index is.
15	As a user, I want to zoom in on diagrams, to see more details on the data.
16	As a user, I would like to see graphics about the location of a lake, for example aerial views.
17	As a user, I would like to understand how data was generated/ measured, to decide if the data quality is sufficient for my concern.
18	As a user, I want to be able to see in the data when certain measures have been taken (e.g. phosphorus precipitation) in order to better understand the data.
19	As a user, I want to select and deselect single parameters to be displayed or hidden in the charts.
20	As a user, I want to generate graphics with multiple y-axes, to compare different data set (e.g. oxygen content with the pH value).
21	As a user, I want to be able to download data, to evaluate the data differently.
22	As a user, I want to be informed on how the data quality and completeness is guaranteed, to be able to trust the data.
23	As a user, I want to be able to share certain data with selected stakeholders, for example teammates, to be able to discuss the data.
24	As a user, I want to add text to uploaded data or to a certain lake, for example information about relevant actions (for example sludge removal) performed at the lake, for others to be informed about those events.
25	As a user, I want to understand who added text in the context of a certain dataset, or a certain lake, to know who to contact to get more information.
26	As a user, I want to be informed if an oxygen sensor detects a dangerous deviation of the oxygen content in one of the lakes I am responsible for, to avoid fish mortality.
27	As a user, I want to see the parameters for PH Value, ammonium, nitrogen, zoo and phytoplankton, iron content, water level, temperature and depth profile, as part of the description of each lake.

Table 5. Identified User Stories during End-User Evaluation for Pilot 1

The following user story has been identified as no longer relevant based on the end-user feedback as it was mentioned that it is not necessary to compare the water quality of different lakes. These user stories were generated during the Pilot Kick-Off Workshop.

Number	User Story	Source
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7	As a user, I want to compare the current data of this lake to historical data, to understand how the condition of the lake changes.	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop
8	As a user, I would like to compare up to 5 small lakes in terms of all values that were also visible in the detail view to identify differences.	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop
9	As a user, I want to see a list of all the small lakes so I can select and deselect the lakes I want to compare.	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop

Table 6. User stories identified as no longer relevant after End-User Evaluation for Pilot 1

3.3 IDENTIFIED USER STORIES – PILOT 2

Number	User Story
15	As a user, I would like to know how the shown connectivity map is calculated.
16	As a user, I would like to know how trustworthy or uncertain the calculation of connectivity is.
17	As a user, I would like to see an indicator at which spatial resolution the map is calculated.
18	As a user, I would like to select between different types of land use (Forest, Shrubland, Crops, Herbaceous crops, Woody crops, Aquatic).
19	As a user, I would like to see which filters are affecting the connectivity map and which filters are only layers on top of connectivity map.
20	As a user, I would like to see when a layer was last updated and from which year the information is.
21	As a user, I would like to have a layer that shows the cadastral information of the area.
22	As a user, I would like to decide whether I want the coordinates shown on the map or not.
23	As a user, I would like to enter a land use change that possibly improves connectivity (e.g. animal crossing).
24	As a user, I would like to change land uses to different types enter different land use changes (road, urban area, industrial area, channels, railroads, wildlife crossing, habitat restoration, forest, crops, shrublands, woody crops, herbaceous crops, aquatic).
25	As a user, I would like to change land use by selecting an area by dropping pins that automatically connect.
26	As a user, I would like to change the position of the set pins when creating a new scenario.
27	As a user, I would like to enter a land use change by entering different coordinates.
28	As a user, I would like to see the cadastral information when selecting the area.
29	As a user, I would like to see all my scenarios that I have created.
30	As a user, I would like to delete scenarios that I have created.
31	As a user, I would like to save my created scenarios.

Table 7. Identified User Stories during End-User Evaluation for Pilot 2

No user stories from the pilot kick-off have been identified as not relevant, as none of them have been mentioned as unnecessary.

3.4 IDENTIFIED USER STORIES – GENERAL USER INTERFACE

Number	User Story
38	As a user, I would like to have the option of inviting certain institutions to the Data Space if I believe that their data is missing from the Data Space.
39	As a user, I would like to be able to set a filter to view only validated data sets.
40	As a user, I would like to receive a message (by email) for certain filters that I have set when a new data set appears that matches my preferences so that I don't miss any relevant data sets.
41	As a user, I would like to see on the dataset detail page for which paper the dataset was used as a basis in order to better assess its relevance for my own needs.

Table 8. Identified User Stories during End-User Evaluation for the general User Interface

The following user story has been identified as no longer relevant based on the end-user feedback, as it was mentioned that it is not necessary to know when a dataset has been last modified. This user story was generated during the context analysis (Deliverable 1.1).

Number	User Story	Source
5	As a researcher, I would like to see when the data set was last modified to determine if I have the most recent data.	Deliverable 1.1

Table 9. User stories identified as no longer relevant after End-User Evaluation for the General User Interface

4. FINAL USER REQUIREMENTS (UR)

Throughout the Human-Centered Design (HCD) process, user needs were systematically identified and initially documented as user stories. These user stories served as a structured representation of the needs and expectations of potential users when interacting with the pilot tools. However, to facilitate a final assessment —aimed at determining whether the implemented pilot tools effectively address and satisfy the identified user needs—, all collected user stories were reformulated into user requirements. This transformation was crucial in ensuring that the user needs were articulated in a manner that allows for precise evaluation and verification during the implementation phase.

A user requirement is defined as a necessary user action within an interactive system. Rather than being framed in terms of technical implementation details, user requirements are task-oriented, focusing on what a user needs to achieve rather than how the system should be technically designed [8]. Necessary user actions can be categorized into cognitive abilities, such as the ability to recognize and interpret information, and observable actions, including operations such as selecting, initiating, entering, or modifying content within the system. Each user requirement is directly derived from an underlying user need and describes, in a technology-independent manner, how this need can be fulfilled through interaction with the system.

To ensure that user requirements serve as a reliable basis for evaluation and validation, they must be formulated in a manner that is clear, unambiguous, and verifiable [8]. This is particularly important because user requirements are often referenced in inspection-based assessments, where they are systematically checked against the implemented system to determine whether all identified needs have been properly addressed.

During the process of rephrasing user stories into user requirements, certain refinements were made to improve clarity and verifiability. Some user stories were merged into a single user requirement when they represented closely related needs that could be addressed through a unified interaction. Conversely, in other cases, individual user stories were divided into multiple user requirements to ensure that each requirement was specific and measurable, thus making it possible to assess whether it had been fully met in the final implementation.

To further structure and categorise the collected user requirements, a task-modeling approach was applied. This method organizes user requirements based on the tasks that users aim to accomplish when interacting with the system. By grouping user requirements according to task categories, a more structured and intuitive overview of the collected requirements was achieved, facilitating a clear understanding of how the system is expected to support user interactions.

The following task categories were identified for Pilot 1, Pilot 2, and the General User Interface based on the analysis of user needs:

Pilot 1:

- Log in to the system
- Obtain an overview of the monitored lakes
- Access detailed information about a specific lake
- Download a dataset related to a lake
- Provide feedback on a dataset

Pilot 2:

- Learn about the functionalities of the BioConnect Tool

- View connectivity data
- Modify parameters for connectivity calculations
- Select layers for map
- Create a land-use change scenario
- View results from a land-use change scenario
- Manage a created scenario for future reference
- Export a created scenario for further analysis or external use

General User Interface:

- Log in and become a registered member of the GDDS (Green Deal Data Space)
- Access general information about the GDDS and its purpose
- Search for datasets within the platform
- Initiate a structured search query based on specific criteria
- Access detailed metadata and information about a selected dataset
- Submit a request to obtain access to a dataset
- Download available datasets
- Provide feedback on datasets
- Upload a dataset to contribute to the GDDS
- Learn about and access tools available within the GDDS
- Perform additional interactions not covered by the above categories

By systematically structuring user requirements according to task-based categories, this approach ensures that the collected requirements remain organized, accessible, and actionable throughout the implementation phase. This categorization also facilitates a more efficient validation process, ensuring that each task identified as essential for user interaction has been adequately addressed in the final system design.

In the following sections, all user requirements for Pilot 1, Pilot 2, and the General User Interface are systematically listed. The requirements have been structured in accordance with the task modelling approach outlined earlier, ensuring a logical flow that aligns with the key user interactions within the system. The numbering of the user requirements has been adapted to reflect this structured categorization, maintaining consistency throughout the documentation.

Some of the initial user stories are captured within a single user requirement, while others have been divided into multiple user requirements to ensure clarity and verifiability. To provide traceability and transparency, the <USER STORY REFERENCE> column indicates which original user stories are represented by each specific user requirement. This allows for a clear understanding of how initial user needs have been translated into verifiable and structured requirements. Additionally, the <SOURCE> column specifies where each user story was originally collected, ensuring that the origins of the identified user needs remain documented. Lastly, the <Task Category> shows, which task the user requirement is mapped to.

4.1 UR - PILOT 1 – SPLASHBOARD TOOL

Number	User requirement	User Story Reference	Source	Task category
UR1	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate logging in to the system.	User Story 11	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Log in to the system
UR2	With the system, the user shall be able to	User Story 11	Pilot Kick-Off	Obtain an

	enter data on a specific lake.		Workshop	overview of the monitored lakes
UR3	With the system, the user shall be able to access sensible data (if available for the account).	User Story 11	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Obtain an overview of the monitored lakes
UR4	With the system, the user shall be able to select a lake of interest (e.g. on a map).	User Story 2	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Obtain an overview of the monitored lakes
UR5	With the system, the user shall be able to select different locations to look for a lake.	User Story 13 User Story 16	End-User Evaluation	Obtain an overview of the monitored lakes
UR6	With the system, the user shall be able to enter keywords (e.g. name of the lake) to find a specific lake.	User Story 3 User Story 10	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Obtain an overview of the monitored lakes
UR7	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize a ranking of the lakes in specific area (e.g. all of Berlin, or a specific district) based on water quality.	User Story 6	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Obtain an overview of the monitored lakes
UR8	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the water quality index within the map.	User Story 5	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Obtain an overview of the monitored lakes
UR9	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the water quality of small lakes in the district.	User Story 1 User Story 4	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR10	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the water level of small lakes in the district.	User Story 1 User Story 4	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR11	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of PH Value for each lake.	User Story 27	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR12	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of ammonium for each lake.	User Story 27	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR13	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of nitrogen for each lake.	User Story 27	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR14	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of zoo and phytoplankton for each lake	User Story 27	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake

UR15	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of iron content for each lake.	User Story 27	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR16	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of water temperature for each lake.	User Story 27	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR17	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of depth profile for each lake.	User Story 27	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR18	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize how the water quality index is calculated (Measurement period, Parameters, Calculation method, all seasons...).	User Story 14	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR19	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize how valid the calculated water quality index is.	User Story 14 User Story 22	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR20	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize how the data was generated/ measured.	User Story 17	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR21	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize when a dataset has been created (e.g. timestamp).	User Story 18	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR22	With the system, the user shall be able to select multiple data parameters within the same graph/diagram.	User Story 12 User Story 20	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR23	With the system, the user shall be able to change the parameters for the graph/diagram.	User Story 19	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR24	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize different detail levels within the diagram (e.g. days, weeks, etc.).	User Story 15	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR25	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize when a deviation of oxygen content in a lake has been measured.	User Story 17	End-User Evaluation	Access detailed information about a specific lake
UR26	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate a download of a specific data set.	User Story 21	End-User Evaluation	Download a dataset related to a lake
UR27	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate sharing certain datasets with other members of the system.	User Story 23	End-User Evaluation	Download a dataset related to a lake

UR28	With the system, the user shall be able to enter comments to a specific dataset.	User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Provide feedback on a dataset
UR29	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize who has added a comment to a specific data set.	User Story 25	End-User Evaluation	Provide feedback on a dataset
UR30	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the contact information of other members of the system.	User Story 25	End-User Evaluation	Provide feedback on a dataset

Table 10. Final User Requirements for Pilot 1

4.2 UR - PILOT 2 - BIOCONNECT TOOL

Number	User requirement	User Story Reference	Source	Task Category
UR1	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize what the “BioConnect Tool” is about.	User Story 1	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Learn about the functionalities of the BioConnect Tool
UR2	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate the “BioConnect Tool”.	User Story 2	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Learn about the functionalities of the BioConnect Tool
UR3	With the system, the user shall be able to select specific species to show their connectivity on the map.	User Story 5	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	View connectivity data
UR4	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the type of data that is available.	User Story 6	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	View connectivity data
UR5	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize how the shown connectivity map is calculated.	User Story 15	End-User Evaluation	View connectivity data
UR6	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize how trustworthy (or uncertain) the calculation of connectivity is.	User Story 16	End-User Evaluation	View connectivity data
UR7	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize at which spatial resolution the map is calculated.	User Story 17	End-User Evaluation	View connectivity data
UR8	With the system, the user shall be able to select forest as a type of land use for connectivity calculations.	User Story 18	End-User Evaluation	Modify parameters for connectivity calculations
UR9	With the system, the user shall be able to select shrubland as a type of land use for connectivity calculations.	User Story 18	End-User Evaluation	Modify parameters for connectivity calculations
UR10	With the system, the user shall be able to select herbaceous crops as a type of land	User Story 18	End-User Evaluation	Modify parameters for

	use for connectivity calculations.			connectivity calculations
UR11	With the system, the user shall be able to select woody crops as a type of land use for connectivity calculations.	User Story 18	End-User Evaluation	Modify parameters for connectivity calculations
UR12	With the system, the user shall be able to select aquatic as a type of land use for connectivity calculations.	User Story 18	End-User Evaluation	Modify parameters for connectivity calculations
UR13	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize which filters are affecting the connectivity map.	User Story 19	End-User Evaluation	Modify parameters for connectivity calculations
UR14	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize which filters are only layers on top of the connectivity map.	User Story 19	End-User Evaluation	Select layers for map
UR15	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize when a layer was last updated.	User Story 20	End-User Evaluation	Select layers for map
UR16	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize from what year the information of a layer is.	User Story 20	End-User Evaluation	Select layers for map
UR17	With the system, the user shall be able to select a layer showing the cadastral information of the area.	User Story 21	End-User Evaluation	Select layers for map
UR18	With the system, the user shall be able to select a geometry file with geolocation data to find out what effect certain constructions in specific areas would have on animal connectivity.	User Story 3	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Create a land-use change scenario
UR19	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize instruction on how to upload a file (e.g. what format is required).	User Story 4	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Create a land-use change scenario
UR20	With the system, the user shall be able to enter a land use change scenario to see its impact on connectivity.	User Story 8	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Create a land-use change scenario
UR21	With the system, the user shall be able to change the setting on whether to see the coordinates on the map.	User Story 22	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR22	With the system, the user shall be able to enter road as a land use change.	User Story 23	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR23	With the system, the user shall be able to enter urban area as a land use change.	User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR24	With the system, the user shall be able to enter industrial area as a land use change.	User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR25	With the system, the user shall be able to enter channels as a land use change.	User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change

				scenario
UR26	With the system, the user shall be able to enter railroads as a land use change.	User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR27	With the system, the user shall be able to enter wildlife crossing as a land use change.	User Story 23 User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR28	With the system, the user shall be able to enter habitat restoration as a land use change.	User Story 23 User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR29	With the system, the user shall be able to enter forest as a land use change.	User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR30	With the system, the user shall be able to enter crops as a land use change.	User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR31	With the system, the user shall be able to enter shrublands as a land use change.	User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR32	With the system, the user shall be able to enter woody crops as a land use change.	User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR33	With the system, the user shall be able to enter herbaceous crops as a land use change.	User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR34	With the system, the user shall be able to enter aquatic as a land use change.	User Story 24	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR35	With the system, the user shall be able to enter a specific area for a land use change.	User Story 25	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR36	With the system, the user shall be able to change the position of the det pins when creating a new scenario.	User Story 26	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR37	With the system, the user shall be able to enter an area for land use change by entering different coordinates.	User Story 27	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR38	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the cadastral information when selecting an area for land use change.	User Story 28	End-User Evaluation	Create a land-use change scenario
UR39	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the connectivity in a scenario over time to also see the future impact.	User Story 11	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	View results from a land-use change scenario
UR40	With the system, the user shall be able to select multiple scenarios in order to compare them.	User Story 12	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	View results from a land-use change scenario
UR41	With the system, the user shall be able to change the parameters of the created	User Story 10	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	View results from a land-

	scenario to be able to view different land uses.			use change scenario
UR42	With the system, the user shall be able to create a scenario (map).	User Story 7	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Manage created scenario for future reference
UR43	With the system, the user shall be able to name a scenario (map).	User Story 7	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Manage created scenario for future reference
UR44	With the system, the user shall be able to change the name of a scenario (map).	User Story 7	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Manage created scenario for future reference
UR45	With the system, the user shall be able to share a scenario (map).	User Story 7	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Manage created scenario for future reference
UR46	With the system, the user shall be able to enter text comments in a certain area of a scenario (map).	User Story 9	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Manage created scenario for future reference
UR47	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate an export of a created scenario (map) to a local file system.	User Story 13 User Story 14	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Export a created scenario for further analysis or external use
UR48	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize all scenarios that were created.	User Story 29 User Story 31	End-User Evaluation	Manage created scenario for future reference
UR49	With the system, the user shall be able to delete scenarios that were created.	User Story 30	End-User Evaluation	Manage created scenario for future reference

Table 11. Final User Requirements for Pilot 2

4.3 UR - GENERAL USER-INTERFACE

Number	User requirement	User Story Reference	Source	Task Category
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UR1	With the system, the user shall be able to enter sign up information to become a member of the GDDS.	User Story 31 User Story 37	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Log in and become a registered member of the GDDS
UR2	With the system the user shall be able to initiate a request to become a member of the GDDS.	User Story 31	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Log in and become a registered member of the GDDS (Green Deal Data Space)
UR3	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize other members of the GDDS.	User Story 30	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Log in and become a registered member of the GDDS (Green Deal Data Space)
UR4	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate an invitation to other institutions to become a member of the GDDS.	User Story 38	End-User Evaluation	Log in and become a registered member of the GDDS (Green Deal Data Space)
UR5	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the functionality of the GDDS.	User Story 16	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Access general information about the GDDS and its purpose
UR6	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize different research fields the GDDS has been used in.	User Story 32	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Access general information about the GDDS and its purpose
UR7	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize publications in context of the GDDS.	User Story 33	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Access general information about the GDDS and its purpose
UR8	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize different datasets based on location.	User Story 1 User Story 19	Deliverable 1.1 Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Search for datasets within the platform
UR9	With the system, the user shall be able to enter geographical coordinates to find specific datasets.	User Story 21	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Search for datasets within the platform
UR10	With the system, the user shall be able to enter keywords to find specific datasets.	User Story 2	Deliverable 1.1	Initiate a structured search query based on specific criteria
UR11	With the system, the user shall be able to select datasets based on licences, format, time period, EVs and provider.	User Story 20 User Story 22	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Initiate a structured search query

		User Story 23		based on specific criteria
UR12	With the system, the user shall be able to select only validated data sets.	User Story 39	End-User Evaluation	Initiate a structured search query based on specific criteria
UR13	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate a previous used search query.	User Story 17 User Story 18	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Initiate a structured search query based on specific criteria
UR14	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize when a new dataset according to the saved search query is added to the GDDS.	User Story 40	End-User Evaluation	Initiate a structured search query based on specific criteria
UR15	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize what metadata (e.g. Resolution, Boundary Box, etc.) is included in a dataset.	User Story 3 User Story 4 User Story 7 User Story 26	Deliverable 1.1	Access detailed metadata and information about a selected dataset
UR16	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize which data model is used for a specific dataset.	User Story 26	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Access detailed metadata and information about a selected dataset
UR17	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the title, the author, country of publication and EVs of the dataset.	User Story 8 User Story 24	Deliverable 1.1 Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Access detailed metadata and information about a selected dataset
UR18	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize whether a dataset is protected by any licences.	User Story 25	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Access detailed metadata and information about a selected dataset
UR19	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize whether a dataset is validated.	User Story 24	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Access detailed metadata and information about a selected dataset
UR20	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize datasets that are similar to the dataset selected.	User Story 9	Deliverable 1.1	Access detailed metadata and information about a selected dataset

UR21	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize historical datasets (e.g. meteorological, geological).	User Story 10	Deliverable 1.1	Access detailed metadata and information about a selected dataset
UR22	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize a data preview .	User Story 28	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Access detailed metadata and information about a selected dataset
UR23	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate a comparison between different dataset previews.	User Story 29	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Access detailed metadata and information about a selected dataset
UR24	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate a request to a private/confidential dataset.	User Story 11	Deliverable 1.1	Submit a request to obtain access to a dataset
UR25	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate a download of the requested data.	User Story 27	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Download available datasets
UR26	With the system, the user shall be able to enter feedback on a dataset for validation.	User Story 6	Deliverable 1.1	Provide feedback on datasets
UR27	With the system, the user shall be able to enter datasets to share with other GDDS members.	User Story 13 User Story 14	Deliverable 1.1	Upload a dataset to contribute to the GDDS
UR28	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize what tools can be used within the GDDS.	User Story 34	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Learn about and access tools available within the GDDS
UR29	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize whether a tool within the GDDS is relevant to his work.	User Story 34	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Learn about and access tools available within the GDDS
UR30	With the system, the user shall be able to select a tool within the GDDS.	User Story 35	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Learn about and access tools available within the GDDS
UR31	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize under which licence a tool can be used.	User Story 36	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Learn about and access tools available within the GDDS

UR32	With the system, the user shall be able to select main functionalities such as “Explore Data”, “Become a Network Member”, “Activities”, “Tools” and login, in order to fulfil my task.	User Story 15	Pilot Kick-Off Workshop	Perform additional interactions not covered by the above categories
UR33	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize in what use cases the dataset has been applied already.	User Story 41	End-User Evaluation	Perform additional interactions not covered by the above categories
UR34	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate the harmonization of data that derive from different data sources.	User Story 12	Deliverable 1.1	Perform additional interactions not covered by the above categories

Table 12. Final User Requirements for the General User Interface

5. CONCLUSION & NEXT STEPS

Throughout the duration of this project a total of 115 user requirements were systematically gathered throughout the different stages at the process (30 user requirements for Pilot 1, 49 user requirements for Pilot 2, 34 user requirements for General User Interface). The process of gathering these user requirements followed a structured, iterative approach that evolved over the course of the project, incorporating input from stakeholders and potential end users at multiple stages to ensure that the tools developed align with real-world needs.

In the early phases of the project, the first set of user stories was collected as part of a stakeholder analysis, which primarily focused on the overall goals and requirements of the GDDS rather than differentiating between the individual pilots. This initial step provided a broad understanding of user needs and expectations, forming the foundation for subsequent refinements. As the project progressed to the Pilot Kick-Off Workshop, the approach was adjusted to allow for a more granular collection of requirements, shifting the focus toward pilot-specific user needs. This change ensured that the distinct challenges and requirements associated with each pilot were more thoroughly addressed. Nevertheless, the General User Interface remained a key aspect of consideration throughout this phase, ensuring that it was not neglected while also tailoring functionalities to the specific pilots.

Following the refinement of user requirements during the Pilot Kick-Off phase, further validation and expansion of these insights took place through prototyping and evaluation sessions with potential end users. Low-fidelity prototypes of the tools were developed and subsequently presented to users in structured walkthrough sessions, allowing for a critical assessment of the design and functionality. During these evaluations, additional user needs were identified, leading to the formulation of new user stories that were incorporated into the requirement framework. At the same time, certain previously documented user stories were removed from consideration, as they were determined to be irrelevant, redundant, or misaligned with the actual needs and workflows of the intended users. This process of refinement underscores the iterative nature of Human-Centered Design (HCD), where continuous user involvement helps shape a solution that truly reflects their expectations and practical requirements.

All gathered user needs, initially documented as user stories, were subsequently refined and reworded into user requirements to ensure clarity, unambiguity, and verifiability. This transformation was essential to eliminate any potential misinterpretations and to establish a structured, measurable framework that facilitates implementation and evaluation.

At this stage of the project, the gathering of user requirements has officially concluded, as the focus is now shifting towards the implementation for both Pilot 1 and Pilot 2. The insights derived from user research and evaluation serve as a foundation for the development and deployment of the tools, ensuring that the solutions created align with the defined user needs. However, while the requirement collection process is complete within the scope of this project, it is important to acknowledge that future iteration phases may be necessary to further improve and enhance the tools. While this is beyond the current project's scope, potential future developments could involve, for instance, the installation of additional sensors within lakes for Pilot 1 or the integration of more connectivity data for the BioConnect Tool. Such advancements would provide new opportunities to refine and expand the tools, thereby increasing their functionality and applicability. Nonetheless, any further improvements should always be conducted in close collaboration with end users, ensuring that the development remains user-centered and provides tangible value to those interacting with the system. For the General User Interface, the collection of user requirements can provide a comprehensive basis for future implementation.

The General User Interface was conceptualized and developed in response to the user needs identified during the co-design activities. However, the interface was designed without direct alignment to the

current architecture and technical structure of the data space connector. The existing connector implementation is characterized by a high degree of technical complexity, exposing low-level configurations, protocol-specific parameters, and requiring domain knowledge for setup and operation. Consequently, the connector in its current form is not suitable for non-technical stakeholders and presents significant usability barriers. In contrast, the General User Interface serves as a conceptual prototype for a future connector interface that emphasizes user-centric design principles, abstraction of technical complexity, and intuitive interaction patterns. It illustrates how a data space connector could be re-envisioned to support accessible orchestration, data access, and interoperability functionalities without demanding deep technical expertise from end users.

While the General User Interface was conceptualized independently from the current connector architecture, the elicitation of user needs revealed significant overlaps with core functionalities typically offered by a data space connector. Several identified user requirements reflect essential capabilities such as dataset discovery, metadata visibility, access control, and request management. For instance, users expressed the need to recognize other members of the GDDS, search for datasets based on location, geographical coordinates, or keywords, and filter datasets according to licenses, formats, time periods, environmental variables (EVs), and providers. Furthermore, users emphasized the importance of distinguishing between validated and non-validated datasets, inspecting available metadata attributes (e.g., resolution, boundary box), understanding licensing constraints, and initiating access or download requests for protected datasets. These needs align closely with fundamental connector functionalities, such as catalog services for dataset search and retrieval, metadata enrichment, and enforcement of data governance policies. Particularly in relation to privacy and access management, user requirements highlighted the necessity for connectors to support controlled access to confidential datasets, ensuring that data is not automatically accessible to all participants but governed by appropriate authorization mechanisms. Hence, even though the General User Interface represents a future-oriented vision detached from current technical limitations, it inherently addresses and extends many core principles embedded within the connector's role in a federated data space ecosystem. However, outside the scope of this work was to match different technologies to the user requirements and to investigate alternative technologies that may also fulfill the user requirements, potentially offering simpler or more cost-effective solutions than data space components.

As the project approaches its final stages, the collected user requirements will play a crucial role in evaluating the completeness and effectiveness of the implementation. Specifically, for Pilot 1 and Pilot 2, a final inspection phase will take place to verify whether all identified user requirements have been adequately addressed within the implementation process. Meanwhile, for the General User Interface, the design proposal will be carefully assessed against the documented user requirements to ensure that the proposed solutions align with user expectations and usability objectives. By rephrasing user stories into explicit user requirements, we ensured that each requirement can be objectively assessed against the final implementation, allowing for a systematic verification of whether the identified needs were fully addressed. This inspection on whether the user requirements have been considered will be outlined and detailed in the Deliverable 6.2, which is due by the end of the project.

By maintaining a structured and user-driven approach throughout the project, the development of GDDS tools remains firmly rooted in real-world user needs. The iterative nature of requirement gathering, and evaluation has ensured that insights gained at each phase have directly contributed to the refinement, prioritization, and validation of design choices. While the formal process of collecting user requirements has now concluded, the established methodology provides a strong foundation for potential future iterations and enhancements, ensuring that the GDDS solutions remain relevant, usable, and valuable for their intended users over time.

6. REFERENCES

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